

THE SIGNIFICANCE TODAY OF INCORPORATING THE NATIONAL IDEA AND EDUCATION IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM IN NEW UZBEKISTAN STUDENTS

**SAIDOVA MAHLIYO NORMURADOVNA
TASHKENT CITY, OLMAZOR DISTRICT
DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC EDUCATION
METHODIST OF SOCIAL SCIENCES**

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda o'quvchi-yoshlarga milliy g'oyani singdirilishi, Vatanparlik ruhida tarbiyalashda sharq mutafakkirlarning yondoshuvlari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Annotation: In this article, the ideas of Eastern thinkers are discussed in the inculcation of the national idea in the students today, and the education in the spirit of patriotism.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается подход восточных мыслителей к привитию национальной идеи учащимся сегодня, воспитанию их в духе патриотизма.

The goal of the fundamental changes implemented in our country is to implement reforms that will determine the future of our country, its prosperity and development, and the place and influence of Uzbekistan in the world. The transition of society from one stage of development and a certain system of values to the second stage of development and a new system of values, progressive ideas taking place in the mind and thinking of young people, transformation of reforms into positive changes, social phenomena that meet the requirements of civilization, training of highly qualified personnel that meet the requirements of the time depends.

The formation of the spirituality of students is the most important direction of the reforms being carried out in the education system today, and it is an important socio-pedagogical problem. In this regard, scientific and creative works serve as an important criterion for inculcating our national idea in the minds of young people. Such as the universal changes being implemented in our country in educating young people in the spirit of national ideals and patriotism, the achievements, the growth of the potential and opportunities of our people, their participation in the processes of international integration through the achievements of modern science, and their participation in the global changes in the world with their appropriate actions. scientific developments including criteria are also important. At the moment, the current rapid pace of development requires the development of the human personality, his worldview, and his abilities. Taking these factors into account when instilling our national idea into the minds of young people will expand their worldview, raise their intellectual abilities, and increase their political and legal culture. This will serve to

raise conscious, educated and capable young people in every way for the society, to create conditions for them to find their rightful place in life.

Education of healthy ideas means education of high outlook and faith. A worldview is a set of knowledge, imagination and ideas transformed into an organized, coherent conscious system, which invites a person to take a worthy place in society while preserving his identity.

After all, it is clear to us that the national idea, which has been living in our minds and consciousness for a long time, will help us, that its formation will be carried out in the national education and training system, and that it is the youth who have hopes for the future. This means loyalty to the Motherland, love for national values and traditions, kindness to loved ones, loyalty to the chosen path - profession, profession and faith in young people. New thinking and new thinking are responsible for the national consciousness, education and belief, which has been nurtured and refined in the spirit of the ideology of independence.

That is why our forefathers took into account the characteristics of the human personality in the matter of education. As Abu Nasr Farabi, one of our great thinkers, wrote, it is necessary to study the personal characteristics of the students before starting the work of education.

The great thinker in his work "On the Attainment of Happiness" gives a detailed opinion about the method of learning knowledge. According to Farabi's teachings, a person acquires spiritual and moral qualities, moral standards and professional skills with the help of education. He put forward methods of encouragement, habituation, and coercion in education. These methods, in turn, should serve for the education of a morally pure and perfect generation in Farabi's "Society of Virtuous People".

In the "Avesta", which is the basis of the national education and training system, which has a history of 3000 years, the rules of education and upbringing of children are described in the following order: "religious and moral education, physical education, teaching to read and write..."

Farabi is considered to be the thinker who defined education for the first time. The word "education" means to teach a person, to give theoretical knowledge based on explanation, to teach moral norms and practical skills necessary to acquire human virtue and a certain profession, says the scientist. Scholars who lived after the 9th-10th centuries also did a lot of work on the issue of human morality and youth education. Scholars of the world of Sufism, Najmiddin Kubro, Fariddin Attar, Bakhovuddin Naqshband, Ahmed Yassavi, Jalaliddin Rumi, Abdurrahman Jami, Aziziddin Nasafi, Alisher Navoi and others contributed a lot to this good work. Thanks to the creative activity and rich spirituality of these scholars, the foundations of the national education system were created. .

When it comes to education, especially national education, it is necessary to dwell on the essence of this concept. The word tarbiya is of Arabic origin and means "to take care of, to educate, to teach". An educator is a person who implements the above goals. Perfect upbringing is a subjective factor for the development of all aspects of spiritual maturity, and also creates a basis for it. Therefore, in all eras, educators have tried to shape young people's

morals and manners, faith and conscience, knowledge and skills in harmony with the requirements and needs of the time. Accordingly, "any educational process is ultimately ideological education according to its purpose and essence. A healthy ideological education means a high worldview and faith education. It should not be forgotten that education and the personal quality of the teacher and his dedication to his work are extremely important in this matter. Ghazali writes in this regard. "The key to raising the murid of a sheikh (educator) is like a farmer cleaning his surroundings of weeds and thorns in order for a blessing to grow from the ground to give a good harvest."

Today, large-scale reforms are being carried out in the field of education in our country, and these things are being organized in proportion to the education of a well-rounded generation that will ensure its global development for the bright future of our country. To carry out these processes, our country has enough material and technical base, as well as human resources. From this point of view, the work of spirituality and enlightenment has become a priority direction of state policy in our country. "The development of high moral qualities in the society, formation of national ideology, education of young people in the spirit of respect for our rich cultural heritage, historical traditions, universal human values, love for the Motherland, loyalty to the ideals of independence are the decisive factors of the reforms implemented in our country," said Ma' in the Decree on the Public Center of Morality and Enlightenment. Cultivation of human qualities in young people is realized through difficult and honorable paths of enlightenment, which leads them to life heights. Young people who enjoy enlightenment fight and serve for the development of society, its stability, peace and well-being.

List of used literature

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